

INTERNATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE FORMATION
OF MAIN PRINCIPLES OF INTERNATIONAL
INFORMATION LAW

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Annotation: This article examines the legal nature of the principles for regulating relations in the international information sphere. The purpose of this article is to disclose the international legal foundations for the formation of principles governing international information law. Based on the set of established international legal norms in the field of international information exchange, sectoral principles of international information law are identified.

Key words: international law, information sphere, international information law, principle of international information law, international information exchange.

In the modern world, the information sphere is one of the most important elements in the development of society, and as a sphere of social life, it has its own legal framework within which relations formed in the information space are regulated both at the national and international levels. It is obvious that international law not only regulates existing international relations in the information sphere, but also expands the space for their higher level of development.

Revealing the essence of the principles of international information law, we note that the fundamental principles of international law are the norms of jus cogens and ergo omnes and have the highest legal force. We agree with the opinion that “the basic principles of modern international law are certainly peremptory

norms, otherwise they would lose their fundamental character” [1]. In addition, it is determined that “all other international legal norms and actions of subjects of international law must comply with the provisions of the fundamental (basic) principles of international law” [2]. E.A. Pushmin determined that “due to their significance as the most important, constitutive principles of international law, the basic principles are the legal basis for the development of international law-making, for the creation of new international legal institutions and norms that develop and specify their provisions” [3]. It is rightly noted that “the basic principles of international law are its cardinal provisions”, which “establish the very foundations of the behavior of states in international relations and that, therefore, they must be complied with in all areas of international cooperation” [4]. I.I. Lukashuk calls the basic principles “the most important standards of behavior of states, the violation of which is an encroachment on the functioning of the system of international legal regulation” [5]. G.I. Tunkin understands the basic principles of international law as “the norms of international law of the most general nature” [6]. The basic principles of international law have universal validity. This feature is due to the fact that this set of rules of conduct is mandatory not only for all subjects of international law, but also, firstly, is applicable to all types of legal relations arising in the international field, both traditional and new; secondly, it regulates the activities of participants in international relations in any spatial spheres, regardless of the geographical or other (extraterrestrial) location of these spheres and their legal status; thirdly, it operates without time limits [7].

It is well known that before the adoption of the UN Charter, the question of the basic principles of international law was considered mainly in the doctrine of international law. At present, the fundamental principles of international law are proclaimed and enshrined in the UN Charter, in the Declaration of Principles of International Law of 1970 and in the Declaration of Principles to the Final Act of the CSCE of 1975.

We agree with the opinion that the fundamental principles of modern

international law are a system (subsystem) of initial and interrelated norms of general international law, regulating in a generalized form the behavior of states and other subjects of international law in all spheres of international relations that have a mandatory *jus cogens* and *ergo omnes*) the nature and determining in a concentrated form the main content and purpose of international law [8].

Based on the above, we believe that the principles of international law are the guiding rules of behavior of subjects of international law, arising as a consequence of social practice, the legally established foundations of international law.

The study of the basic principles of international law, its legal aspects allows us to determine the following conclusions, namely, firstly, that the basic principles of international law are the basis of the entire international, including the international legal system, and all actions of subjects of international law must be consistent with the basic principles of international law; secondly, the basic principles of international law are among the norms that have the character of *jus cogens* and *ergo omnes*, and they are characterized by normativity, imperativeness and universality of action; thirdly, the close connection of the basic principles of international law with other norms of international law, its reflection in the national legislation of most states of the world, emphasizes their legal significance, not only at the international level, but also within the national jurisdiction of states; and finally, that the fundamental importance of the basic principles of international law lies, on the one hand, in ensuring the interests of individual states, existing, global social systems as a whole and, on the other, the interests of the entire international community.

The basic principles of international law are mandatory not only in terms of their subject composition, but also, firstly, are applicable to all types of legal relations arising at the international level; secondly, they regulate the activities of participants in international relations in any spatial spheres, regardless of the geographical or other location of these spheres and their legal status; and thirdly, the basic principles of international law apply without time limits [9].

The basic principles of international law form an integral system - a whole, unified and logically non-contradictory set of international legal norms and principles. The structural elements and parts of this totality are interconnected and interdependent. The 1970 Declaration of Principles of MP states that “in interpretation and application, the principles set out above are interrelated and each principle must be considered in the context of all others” [10]. The principles included in the system have individual functions and solve their own problems. This gives each of them a certain autonomy, stability and independence. Principles are carriers of the universal, the individual and the particular. It is rightly noted that the principles can be considered as a generalized and indirect reflection of the laws of international legal communication. Compliance with norms and principles is a necessary condition for the functioning of the system [11]. From this point of view, the principles of international law characterize both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of cooperation between states and the achieved level of their relationships.

The system of modern international law includes various principles and norms. They can be classified according to the degree of generalization, scope of application, subject of legal regulation, etc. Let us note that the principles of international law are in constant development, and their content is constantly being improved. Modern international relations determine the formation of new generally recognized international principles, and since the declaration of the principles in the Final Act, the principle of general and complete disarmament under effective international control and the principle of international environmental protection have been formulated and proven their positive impact on the world. It should also be noted that the sad events of September 11, 2001 very acutely showed such an international problem as international terrorism, and therefore the fight against international terrorism has actually become another international principle, which has the right to independent existence along with the general principle of cooperation.

Note that modern international law, along with the general principles of

international law, also contains sectoral principles. Each branch of international law has its own specific sectoral principles [12].

Based on the characteristic features and legal properties of information, we can make an attempt to formulate the basic principles of legal regulation of public relations in the information sphere. As rightly noted by V.A. Kopylov, “legal regulation of information relations is based on the principles of information law, which are understood as the basic starting points that legally explain and consolidate the objective patterns of social relations manifested in the information sphere”. Thus, we can briefly qualify the following system of principles of information law: the principle of alienation of rights to use information based on the legal property of the physical alienation of information from its creator; the principle of information circulation, which is based on the property of information separability and lies in the fact that information can be circulated as an independent object, i.e. regardless of its creator or owner; the principle of an information object (information thing) or the principle of dual unity of information and its carrier, based on the property of dual unity of information and a material carrier and lies in the fact that such an object should be simultaneously and interconnectedly extended by two institutions: intellectual property, which protects the right to information on a tangible medium, and proprietary property, which protects the right of ownership of a tangible medium with information recorded on it; the principle of information dissemination based on the property of information dissemination and lies in the fact that the same information can simultaneously belong to an unlimited number of persons; the principle of organizational form [12] is based on the property of information of the same name and lies in the fact that in the legal system, as a rule, the discussion should not be about information in general, but about information presented in a certain organizational form. This principle also allows us to classify both individual documents and complex organizational information structures as information objects.

Information as a product of human consciousness is immaterial and can only

exist within a material medium. It is necessary to distinguish between relations regarding information, information carrier and information available on a material medium. Based on the definition of the main features of the concept of “information,” we believe that information is an intangible object, perceived by human consciousness, representing information about phenomena occurring in society and nature, and the process of transmitting specific information or facts to any subject [13].

We should note, that despite existing international agreements in the field of informatization, international law on many issues does not keep up with the challenges that arise as a result of the use of information and communication technologies. Many experts point to such gaps in international information law [14]. The study of the basic principles of legal regulation of relations in the information sphere allows us to identify the main distinctive features of information relations. Due to the fact that an information object consists of information (meaning content) and a material medium, the resulting powers to use, own and dispose of such an object must be exercised subject to the use of additional information powers, including the procedure for creating, owning, using and distributing the information displayed in an information object based on the legal properties of information.

References::

1. Ushakov N.A. International law: Textbook. – M.: Yurist, 2021. – p. 54
2. Fundamental principles of modern international law // International public law: Textbook. – T.: Zarqalam; TGUI, 2003. – p. 84
3. Pushmin E.A. On the legal nature of the principle of peaceful resolution of international disputes // Yearbook of International Law. – M.: Nauka, 1976. – p. 198.
4. Bobrov R.L. Main problems of the theory of international law. – M.: International Relations, 1968. – p. 192-193

5. Lukashuk I.I. International legal regulation of international relations. – M.: International Relations, 1975. – p. 8-9
6. Tunkin G.I. Questions of the theory of international law. – M.: Gosyurizdat, 1962. – p. 157
7. Bekyashev K.A., Volosov M.E. International public law. Workshop. – M.: Prospekt, 2018. – p. 21-22
8. See: International public law. Workshop. Edited by G.Yuldasheva. – T.: Lesson press, 2020. – p.74
9. Bekyashev K.A. International public law. – M.: Prospekt, 2019. – p. 21-22
10. Current international law. In 3 volumes / Comp. Kolosov Yu.M., Krivchikova E.S. Volume 1. – M.: Publishing house of the Moscow Independent Institute of International Law, 1999. – p. 72
11. Ignatenko G.V. International law and social progress. – M.: International Relations, 1972. – p. 118
12. Nugmanov N.A. Nature of methods of legal regulation and principles of international information law // Journal of Law Research. Vol. 7, Issue-2, 2022. – p. 101.
13. Nugmanov N.A. Definition of the concept of information security based on the modern development of ICT // Jurisprudence. 2022, volume 3, issue 6. – p. 95.
14. Nugmanov N.A. International Law Regulation of Cooperation in the Sphere of International Information Exchange // Bulletin of the Volga Region Institute of Administration. Science journal №2 (47), 2015. Saratov. – p.40.

